

ISOMORPHIC AND ALLOMORPHIC FEATURES OF SENTENCE
STRUCTURE ENGLISH AND KOREAN

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Annotation: *Each language has own similarities and differences with other languages, whether they are in the same language family or not. The majority of people thinks English and Korean totally various languages that have nothing in common. However, it is not completely truth. In following information which given in this article will show some similitude and contrast sides of these two languages.*

Keywords: *difference, similarities, phonology, sentence structure phrases, object, subject, verb.*

Introduction. Starting with this two languages background, English depend on a Germanic language family and Korean is an Altaic language family. As its obvious their language families are different [1]. It means their sentence structure, the places of subject, object and verbs also different. But in speaking we can also see some changes rather than writing.

Main body. Isomorphic feature deals with common characters of simple and complex sentences of two or more languages while allomorphic features work on the diversity of the selected languages. People can see this both features in a specific unit of language. They are structural, semantic, pragmatic aspects.

Another difference of English and Korean is formal and informal speech. In Korean language for making formal speech they use 2 different words instead of “I” 저 [cho] for formal situation and 나 [na] for informal situations. After the

subjects they can add two types of suffix. They are (after consonant) 은/(after vowel)는 which are called Topic particles while (after consonant)이/(after vowel)가 that are called – Subject Particles which in English people use to be verb after personal pronouns. Whether their written forms are different like in English it is use to be written separately meanwhile in Korean together, their functions work in the same way.

For example, in the sentence “오늘은 날씨가 좋아요.” subject of the sentence is 날씨 (Weather) while the topic of the sentence is 오늘 (Today).

In fact, in most of the situations 은/는 and 이/가 are interchangeable. ‘이것은 책임니다’ and ‘이것이 책임니다’ are pretty much the same thing.

Emotional expressiveness

In English language, there are ways of expressing sentences with emotions.

For example:

I am not in mood!	기분이(mood) 안(not) 좋아(good)!
Do not make me angry!	날(me) 화나게(angry) 하지마(stop it)!
I do love it!	나는(I) 그것을(it) 사랑 해요(love)!

Inversions in these two languages, there are formative and negative expressive answers.

I enjoyed.	내가(I) 즐겼다(enjoyed).
So do I.	...
Formal	저도요(so do I).

Informal	나도 그래(so do I).
He cannot run.	그는(he) 달릴 수(can run) 없습니다(not).
Neither do I.	...
Formal.	저도(I) 아니에요(neither do i).
Informal.	나도하지(neither do i).

Inversion in both languages in a passive voice with prepositions

The boy was looked after by a babysitter.	찾고 있는 것이 있습니다.
The boy was looked after by a babysitter.	그 소년은 베이비 시터가 돌보았다.

The passive of a population language such as English is mainly treated as a verb problem, but the passive sentence in Korean is primarily a morphological problem because it is determined primarily by the predicate of the sentence. In the study so far, the passive form of the Korean predicate constituting the passive sentence can be organized into four types in terms of morphology, and the types and examples are as follows.

(1) 파동형식의 유형

Types of prefixes

가. 타동사 어간 + '이, 히, 리, 기' 도둑이 포교한테 잡히었다.

[da] Transitive verb stem + 'Lee, Hee, Lee, Gi' A thief was caught by propaganda.

나. 자동사 소가 농부에게 맞았다.

[na] Auto-death cow was hit by a farmer.

다. 용언어간 + '아/어' + '지다'; 수양제가 을지문덕에게 깨뜨려지다.

Suyangje is broken by Eulji Mundeok.

라. 명사성어근+ '되다' 그 사람의 글이 신문에 게재되었다.

[la] Noun root + 'become' Person's writing was published in the newspaper [2].

Conclusion. All above considered, there are many similarities and differences of English and Korean. As it is mentioned above, there are different words orders in sentence structure which makes languages clear. People can realize the versatility of specific language by making scientific research on language.

The list of used literature:

1. Hong Jeong-ha, Computational realization of the Korean passive type', (Department of Language Science, Korea University) P-130
2. *thesis was made with support from the Korea Research Foundation's Leading Researcher Support Project (Research Director: Ki-Yong Lee) in 1999.
3. <https://asiasociety.org/education/korean-language>
4. <https://www.topikguide.com/difference-between-%EC%9D%80%EB%8A%94-and-%EC%9D%B4%EA%B0%80/>